

APPENDIX. MEASUREMENT ITEMS

Relationship orientation

Trust

1. The logistics provider keeps the promises he makes to our firm.
2. The logistics provider is genuinely concerned that our business succeeds.
3. When making important decisions, this logistics provider considers our welfare as well as its own.
4. Logistics provider is trustworthy.

Bonding

1. We both try very hard to establish a long-term relationship.
2. We work in close cooperation.
3. We keep in touch constantly.

Communication

1. Our firm and logistics provider have frequent contacts on a regular basis.
2. Our firm and logistics provider have open and two-way communication.
3. Our firm and logistics provider have informal communication.
4. Our firm and logistics provider have many different channels to communicate.

Goal congruence

1. Our firm and logistics provider have agreement on the goals of the supply chain.
2. Our firm and logistics provider have agreement on the importance of collaboration across the supply chain
3. Our firm and logistics provider agree that our own goals can be achieved through working toward the goals of the supply chain.
4. Our firm and logistics provider jointly layout collaboration implementation plans to achieve the goals of the supply chain.

Resource sharing

1. Our firm and logistics provider use cross-organizational teams frequently for process design and improvement.
2. Our firm and logistics provider dedicate personnel to manage the collaborative processes.
3. Our firm and logistics provider share technical supports.
4. Our firm and logistics provider share equipment (e.g. computers, networks, machines).
5. Our firm and logistics provider pool financial and non-financial resources (e.g. time, money, training).

Information sharing

1. Our logistics provider share proprietary information with us.
2. Our logistics provider keeps us fully informed about issues that affect our business.
3. Our logistics provider share business knowledge of core business processes with us.
4. We and our logistics provider keep each other informed about events or changes that may affect the other partner.

Information Technology (IT) integration

IT alignment

1. My company's IT for supply chain improvement is well aligned with our logistics provider.
2. My company invests in IT to align our technology with logistics provider.
3. Our logistics provider invests in IT to align their technology with us.
4. Both my company and our logistics provider always work together for the best IT alignment.

Information sharing

1. Information exchange between our logistics provider and us is timely.
2. Information exchange between our logistics provider and us is accurate.
3. Information exchange between our logistics provider and us is complete.
4. Information exchange between our logistics provider and us is adequate.
5. Information exchange between our logistics provider and us is reliable.

3PL service quality

Timeliness

1. Time between placing an order and receiving delivery from our logistics partner is short.
2. Deliveries arrive on the date that our logistics provider promised.
3. Orders not delivered in time are subsequently sent quickly by our logistics provider.
4. Our logistics provider organizes efficiently the logistics management of product return (reverse logistics).

Order condition

1. Orders rarely arrive damaged by our logistics provider.
2. Order damage rarely occurs as a result of the transport mode of our logistics provider.
3. Order damage rarely occurs as a result of transport carrier handling.
4. Number of "damaged" orders dispatched in a period / total number of orders dispatched in the same period.

Order accuracy

1. Shipments coming from our logistics provider rarely contain the wrong items.
2. Shipments coming from our logistics provider rarely contain an incorrect quantity.
3. Shipments coming from our logistics provider rarely contain substituted items.

Contact quality

1. Product / Service knowledge of our logistics provider's contact employees is sufficient.
2. Our logistics provider's contact employees are able to resolve product / service problems.
3. Our logistics provider's contact employees make efforts to understand my business situation.

Information quality

1. Order information given by our logistics provider is accurate.
2. Order information is available.
3. Our logistics partner provides us the ability to trace the orders. (Traceability)

Discrepancy handling

1. Our logistics provider correct order discrepancies in a satisfactory way.
2. The process that our logistics provider is following for reporting order discrepancies is adequate.
3. The response of our logistics provider to order discrepancies is satisfactory.

Availability

1. If my logistics provider is notified of possible increases in upcoming orders, inventory will be increased to meet orders.
2. Products are consistently available in inventory when ordered to logistics provider.
3. My logistics provider does not impose maximum order size constraints.
4. My logistics provider does not impose order assortment constraints.

Flexibility

1. Our logistics provider is able to change planned delivery dates.
2. Our logistics provider is able to respond to and accommodate demand variations, such as seasonality.
3. We and our logistics provider expect to be able to make adjustments in the ongoing relationship to cope with changing circumstances.
4. When some unexpected situation arises, we and our logistics provider would rather work out a new deal than hold each other to the original terms.

Delivery reliability

1. Traceability.
2. Numbers of orders delivered in the due date.
3. Reliability in order completion process.
4. On time delivery.
5. Order fulfillment lead time.

Customer satisfaction

1. We are delighted with the overall distribution service relationships with our logistics provider.
2. We are getting desired service quality for the price it is charging from our logistics provider.
3. We perceive that we are getting greater value for the price we paying for our logistics provider.
4. We are always satisfied with the cost / performance ratio of our logistics provider's service.
5. I think I did the right thing when I chose this logistics provider for its service.
6. We are always satisfied with our interactions with our logistics provider's service.
7. We are satisfied with the overall experience of our logistics provider's services.

Mutual loyalty

1. The relationship that my firm has with this logistics provider is something we are very committed to.
2. I believe our logistics provider is very committed to our relationship.
3. The relationship that my firm has with this distributor is something we intend to maintain indefinitely.
4. I believe our logistics provider is intents to maintain our relationship indefinitely.
5. The relationship that my firm has with this distributor deserves our maximum effort to maintain.
6. I believe our logistics provider makes maximum efforts in order to maintain our relationship.
7. Maintaining a long-term relationship with this distributor is very important to my firm.
8. I believe our logistics provider thinks that maintaining a long-term relationship with us is very important.
9. I would recommend that my successor continue using this distributor.
10. I believe our logistics provider wish to continue our relationship in the future.

Supply chain performance

Delivery reliability

1. We deliver customer orders in time.
2. The delivery of our products is executed rapidly.
3. We always deliver the correct quantity with the right kind of products.
4. It is probable that products are in stock at order time.

Flexibility

1. Our firm with supply chain partners offers variety of products and services efficiently in comparison with industry norms.
2. Our firm with logistics provider offers customized products and services with different features quickly in comparison with industry norms.
3. Our firm with logistics provider meets different customer volume requirements efficiently in comparison with industry norms.
4. Our firm with logistics provider has good customer responsiveness in comparison with industry norms.

Responsiveness

1. Our company is able to fulfill customer orders on time.
2. Our company is capable to maintain short customer order cycle time.
3. We can support our customers before each sale.
4. In case of defective products, we can easily make amendments, even immediately replace them.
5. We can offer after-sales service to our customers.
6. Our customers know that our company responds quicker to their needs.

Lean production

1. Our key suppliers deliver to our plants on just in time (JIT) basis.
2. Our key suppliers are located in close proximity to our plants.
3. We use a “pull” production system.
4. Pace of production is directly linked with the rate of customer demand.
5. We have low setup times in our plants.
6. We make extensive use of statistical techniques to reduce process variance.
7. We almost never keep redundant products in stock.
8. We maintain excellent records of all equipment maintenance related activities.

Mass customization

1. We are highly capable of large scale product customization.
2. We can easily add significant product variety without increasing cost.
3. We can customize products while maintaining high volume.
4. We can add product variety without sacrificing quality.
5. Our capability for responding quickly to customization requirements is very high.

Schedule attainment

1. We usually meet the production schedule each day.
2. Our daily schedule is reasonable to complete on time.
3. We cannot adhere to our schedule on a daily basis.
4. It seems like we are always behind schedule.

Efficiency

1. Our firm with supply chain partners meets agreed upon unit costs in comparison with industry norms.
2. Our firm with supply chain partners meets productivity standards in comparison with industry norms.
3. Our firm with supply chain partners meets on-time delivery requirements in comparison with industry norms.
4. Our firm with supply chain partners meets inventory requirements in comparison with industry norms.

Competitive advantage

1. We are first in the market in introducing new products.
2. We have time-to-market lower than industry average.
3. We have fast product development.
4. Our products offer unique benefits than competitors.
5. Our products have superior quality than competitors.
6. Our products are more advanced than those in the same market.
7. Our products are differentiated from competitors' products.

Firm performance

Financial performance

1. Return on investment (ROI).
2. Profit margin on sales.
3. Return on Assets (ROA).
4. % revenues from new products.
5. Return on Sales (ROS).

Market share performance

1. Growth of sales.
2. Market share.
3. Growth in Market share.
4. Overall competitive position.

Customer satisfaction

1. Our customers are pleased with the products and services we provide for them.
2. We have a large number of repeat customers.
3. We generate new customers in our firm on a regular basis.
4. We hardly receive complaints about our service offering.

Firm efficiency

1. We make use of our staff members to the best of their abilities.
2. We make maximum use of physical facilities.
3. We monitor timeliness of service delivery.
4. We make optimal use of financial resources.
5. Benchmark comparisons are made of the progress achieved in our firm.
6. High quality administrative systems are in place to support the efficiency of the firm.

Financial viability

1. Our profit margins have been increasing over the years.
2. We pay our suppliers on time.
3. Our firm consistently has more revenue than expenses.
4. Our firm keeps a reasonable surplus of money to use during difficult times.
5. Our assets are greater than liabilities.
6. Our firm diversifies levels of funding sources.